

DiSSCo Transition Project

First user and technical stakeholder workshops on standards in support of the development in WP3

Work Package 4 - Milestone 19

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Executive Summary

In the DiSSCo Transition project, WP4 “International Collaboration on (data) Standards” has the objective of supporting continued development and adoption of new community standards. As part of WP4 work, we prepared and ran the first user workshop for the newly ratified Latimer Core (LtC) data standard. Preparation included: selecting a freely available system that we could implement LtC in (Airtable); creating generic LtC templates that would be suitable for different uses; creating reference content based on a real use case (collections audit prior to specimen-level digitisation) at the NHM; creating workshop content including a presentation and orientation/exercises for participants.

We delivered the workshop to 15-20 participants in a hybrid workshop at the SPNHC-TDWG 2024 Conference in Okinawa, Japan on September 4th, 2024.

All workshop material was made available in Zenodo under a permissive license. The workshop material was designed to be re-usable/customisable for future workshops.

Keywords

Latimer Core (LtC), Data standards, User Workshop, Digital collections management

1. Summary / Introduction

In the DiSSCo Transition project, Workpackage 4 (WP4) “International Collaboration on (data) Standards” has the objective of supporting continued development and adoption of new community standards. As part of WP4 work, we prepared and ran the first user workshop for the newly ratified Latimer Core (LtC) data standard. Preparation included: selecting a freely available system that we could implement LtC in (Airtable); creating generic LtC templates that would be suitable for different uses; creating reference content based on a real use case (collections audit prior to specimen-level digitisation) at the NHM; creating workshop content including a presentation and orientation/exercises for participants.

Preparation was done in collaboration with the TDWG Collections Descriptions (CD) Task Group, a community group which developed the LtC data standard.

We delivered the workshop to 15-20 participants in a hybrid workshop at the SPNHC-TDWG 2024 Conference in Okinawa, Japan on September 4th, 2024.

All workshop material was made available in Zenodo under a permissive CC-BY 4.0 license (Livermore, L., Woodburn, M., & Norton, B. (2024)). The workshop material was designed to be re-usable/customisable for future workshops.

2. Workshop Objectives

The workshop had the following five objectives for participants:

1. Understand how Latimer Core (LtC) can be used and how you might use it
2. Become familiar with the Latimer Core data structure
3. Create your own Latimer Core dataset that you can continue to edit after the workshop
4. Give feedback on how we can support you implement new standards for your work
5. Understand how you can participate in standards development

3. Workshop Preparation

Content preparation consisted of four parts:

1. **Technical**
 - a. *Platform* - Latimer Core is a complex hierarchical standard and requires database functionality to properly implement and use. We chose to run the training using *Airtable*, a cloud-based spreadsheet-database hybrid. This allowed us to create prototypes and run training with free accounts without complex hosting or permission management.
 - b. *Airtable Bases* - Latimer Core was designed to cover a range of use cases, with the concept that users/implementers are likely to use a subset of its functionality depending on purpose. We created two *Airtable Bases* – essentially templates – for the training. One base is effectively an empty template without data that represents the complete scope of Latimer Core. It was intended to act as a basis for users to test out different use cases. The second base is a real-world template complete with data, used for planning and tracking the digitisation of NHM London's British and Irish Coleoptera dry, pinned insect collection.
2. **Presentation (PowerPoint)** – the presentation was based on a previous overview of the Latimer Core standard given to the 2024 NatSCA Conference (Livermore and Woodburn, 2024) but with additional slides for orientation and task-based exercises to supplement the documentation.
3. **Documentation (PDF)** – orientation information for users on the Latimer Core standard with links to *Airtable Bases* and a set of structured tasks to help users become familiar with the Latimer Core standard and add their own data.
4. **Survey** – A user feedback survey built in Google Forms.
5. **Closed testing and feedback** – We asked members of the TDWG Collections Descriptions (CD) Task Group to give feedback on the presentation and documentation. Shelley James did complete testing of our test version of documentation for which we are very grateful!

4. Workshop Structure / Agenda

The workshop was around 90 minutes long and included the following sections:

- Introduction ~ 5 minutes
 - Objectives & outcomes

- o Standards work in DiSSCo Transition
- Overview of Latimer Core ~15 minutes
- Applications of Latimer Core ~15 minutes
- Orientation and exercises ~45 minutes
- Wrap-up ~10 minutes
 - o Discussion & feedback
 - o Resources and acknowledgements

5. Workshop Participants

The workshop had around 15-20 participants from three continents (Europe, North America, Asia). There was a sign-up sheet but there were additional attendees on the day.

Known/registered participants were a mix of collections staff (e.g., curators/collection managers), technical staff (e.g., working for GBIF on GRSciColl), and commercial technology/service suppliers.

6. Workshop Delivery

The workshop was delivered as a hybrid workshop run via Zoom at the Okinawa Convention Centre, Japan.

The workshop started with a presentation, then a mix of screensharing and narrative to guide participants through Latimer and our Airtable implementation.

7. Outcomes, Results, Challenges and Lessons Learned

We successfully delivered the course and received good verbal feedback but got no structured survey feedback from participants.

Prior to delivering the course we had already noted that 90 minutes would be tight for delivering both practical overview of the standard and hands-on training in applying it to data. Latimer Core is a complex and structured data standard and would benefit from a slower introduction into the concepts and usage. Time should be factored in to help participants to understand the basic concepts of relational data models as used by LtC, as many in the community are more accustomed to working with relatively flat data in spreadsheet and CSV format. Similarly, if using a structured software tool like Airtable to demonstrate LtC, there should be time allowances to help participants to familiarise themselves with the software before progressing to the LtC-specific parts of the training.

Recommendation 1) For subsequent training, we would recommend at least half a day or ~3 hours of training, which includes familiarisation with structured data concepts and the training tool.

Latimer Core is a new standard, and so far has limited examples of real world applications. While we provided one real example (a digitisation audit use case at NHM London), we recognise that it would be easier for people to understand the potential applications of

LtC if they had more reference examples and templates that align with their own collection description use cases. Some examples raised in the workshop included: recent acquisitions (e.g., collection bequeathments/purchases, field work/expeditions), linking collections with associated archival materials and publications, creating institutional collections profiles for national/transnational programmes (e.g., DiSSCo EU, DiSSCo Flanders and DiSSCo UK).

Recommendation 2) Develop more demonstration templates, with narratives that put them in the context of real-world use cases.

Following on from the previous recommendation, workshop participants requested focused sessions on specific examples that would be relevant to their work.

Recommendation 3) Run specific sessions focused on thematically related sets of use cases.

The workshop included participants with a range of levels of technical proficiency, from relatively basic to highly skilled in systems and data. This often makes it difficult to tailor the training content and pace so that it is most effective for all of the participants. As a new standard, there is also a fairly small number of people who have enough of a grounding in the standard to be able to deliver training, and the demand is likely to outstrip the supply at the present time.

Recommendation 4) Run sessions specific to different stakeholder groups, including train-the-trainer sessions to widen the pool of community resources for LtC training.

The Airtable software is well suited to demonstrating working with structured LtC data, due to the ease of creating relational data tables that closely mirror the structure of the LtC data model and configuring forms on top of the data that demonstrate how it might be managed through a user interface. Workshop participants were provided with the facility to take copies of the demo databases to explore in their own Airtable workspaces in their own time. However, Airtable is a commercial, hosted-only product, and the free tier of licensing has restrictions that make it difficult to scale up to any production application without incurring costs. Other similar no-code options (with differing degrees of maturity and richness of functionality) are available that offer open-source self-hosting options, such as [BaseRow](#), [NocoDB](#) and [Grist](#). These may offer alternative approaches to LtC prototyping and demonstration that also offer a clearer path to scaling up use to production levels.

Recommendation 5) Explore similar technologies to Airtable that have fewer restrictions on use without incurring costs.

8. Future Work / Next Steps

The next steps for the Latimer Core standard itself, and the TDWG Maintenance Group that supports it, are primarily focused on working with stakeholders towards practical applications of the standard. The ability (through the approaches introduced in this workshop) to be able to demonstrate what LtC might look like in a data schema, and how it might look in a corresponding user interface, are important steps in that direction. They should provide some solid ground for focusing conversations with stakeholders from both a technical and an operational perspective. This is also likely to support continued work in Work Package 4 on developing LtC schemas, with associated JSON schemas, that align with DiSSCo EU service requirements and providing a standards-based route to interoperability with other collections data aggregators like national DiSSCo nodes, GRSciColl and the CETAF Registry of Collections.

In terms of next steps for training and developing the demonstration material and platform, we will take the feedback and learnings from the workshop to develop a set of actions to further refine the approach, with reference to the recommendations in the previous section. The route to sustainability is likely to primarily lie with the TDWG Collection Descriptions Interest Group, pending discussions on handover of materials and training/support plans under the TDWG umbrella for the future.

9. Author/Contributor Contributions

Authors:

- Laurence Livermore – Workshop delivery, presentation, survey
- Matt Woodburn – Technical preparation, presentation, documentation
- Ben Norton - Workshop delivery, testing and feedback

Contributors:

- TDWG Collections Descriptions (CD) Task Group – Testing and feedback
- Shelley James, Western Australian Herbarium (Perth) – Workshop delivery, testing and feedback

10. References

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